

Literary and Linguistic Perspectives on English within the Context of Globalization

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Abstract

Within the context of globalization, this study examines literary and linguistic perspectives on the English language. Globalization is essentially about the transformations that the contemporary world encounters. It unifies the scheme of things. While a linguistic overview of globalization examines how shift in societal practices reveal the position and roles of language in nation-building, a literary explanation of globalization captures how globalization influence elements of literature such as theme, language and characterization. Underpinned in the global status and functions of English, this study examines how literary writers and nations benefit from the intrinsic and extrinsic position of the English language in this era of globalization. In spite of the implications of the dominance of English in non-native regions where the language functions as lingua franca, good governance can evolve language policy frameworks to ensure that the development potentials of the world's lingua franca (English) will be maximally explored for nation-building. This study is anchored by two theoretical frameworks: Orisawayi's (2005) Development Parameters and Mani's Concept of "World Literature" cited in Shobha P. (2025). While the former presents development indices that nations should aspire to achieve under good governance, the later contends that external forces (as in globalization trends) impinge on authors' choice and use of elements of literature. The study concludes that globalization does not only foster national development in regions across the world, but also influences literary elements that are deployed in literature texts, with heavy reliance on the broadness of the English lexicon and the global status of English.

Keywords: English, globalization, literary perspective, linguistic perspective, Orisawayi's Development Parameters, Mani's Concept of "World Literature"

1. Introduction

Literary perspectives are perspectives on literature and its major genres: drama, poetry and prose. Such perspectives are often conveyed through literary theories which are established positions on literature. Indeed, as this study is poised to reveal, literary theories are ideal frameworks for elucidating the globalization-related phenomena which literary writers articulate via theme, setting, narrative, language and characterization. Scholars hold the view that literary theories harmonize literary writing (literature) by attempting theoretical categorization of its major concerns, trends and traditions which are potent means of showing not only the influence of globalization on literature, but also the roles of English, which is a chief means of conveying literary writings around the world. In this study, the influence of globalization on literature accentuates the common claim that literature is a product of literary writers' existential experiences rather than existing in a vacuum. Language-related globalization discourse in literary studies does not ignore the significance of English. This study attempts an overview of how the global status of English influences the underpinnings of literary writings and promotes cross-facet development in different regions of the world.

2. Globalization

Globalization is a modern phenomenon. It can be conceptualized in different ways. Steger (2019: 7-8) defines globalization as “the interconnections of global economic, political, cultural and environmental processes that continually transform present conditions.” Chen (2012) highlights five crucial features of globalization:

1. Globalization is a dialectically dynamic process, which is caused by the pushing and pulling off between the two forces of cultural identity and cultural diversity, or between local and global;
2. Globalization is universally persuasive as it penetrates into every aspect of human society and influences the way it lives, thinks, and behaves;
3. Globalization is holistically interconnected as it builds a huge matrix in which all components are interconnected with networks;
4. Globalization represents a culturally hybridized state, which allows cultural transmission via new media to take place at a very rapid rate by permeating and dissolving human boundaries.

Kayode Omole (2016) cited in Ayodabo et al. (2016: 435) defines globalization extensively:

Globalization refers to the universal adoption of social institutions. It is a process by which social institutions or policies become adopted on a world-wide scale. According to Omole (2006), ‘the age of globalization refers to that period of time when certain institutions or policies which may have been peculiar to or characterized certain geopolitical regions of the world or people become extended to or diplomatically imposed on other parts of the world.’ One of the institutions mostly affected by globalization is culture, characterized by the neglect of indigenous languages by African youths and elite. There are many factors responsible for this. Among them are the official status of English and French in many African countries, the founding of many international schools or educational institutions that promote or emphasize the learning of these international languages, massive onslaught of foreign movies and magazine and the elitist aspirations of parents who tend to make English or French the first language of their authentic African children. Given all these social circumstances, Africa’s indigenous languages are being gradually disowned by their speakers.”

The trends which globalization presents to the world are social, scientific, political, etc. Inter-regional interests in such trends spur information sharing and rapid change of ideas and innovations. David Crystal’s (2003: 10) submission is instructive in terms of globalization-related trends:

... economic developments beginning to operate on a global scale supported by the new communication technologies – telegraph, telephone, radio – and fostering the emergence of massive multinational organizations. The growth of competitive industry and business brought an explosion of international marketing and advertising. The power of the press reached unprecedented levels soon to be surpassed by the broadcasting media, with the ability to cross national boundaries with electromagnetic ease. Technology chiefly in the form of movies and records, fueled new mass entertainment industries which had a worldwide impact. The drive to make progress in science and technology fostered an international intellectual research environment which gave scholarship and further education a high profile.

It is worthy of note that globalization structures and value-systems are internationally established as foundational principles for dealing with a wide range of issues, thus making the world a global village.

3. Literary Writing

Literary writing is creative writing as typical of the major genres of literature. In literary writing, language use is enchanting in the narration of human experiences. This view corroborates Moody (1972) who submits that “literature springs from our inborn love of a story, of arranging words in pleasing patterns, of expressing in words some special aspects of our human experience.” Apart from the basic genres of literature mentioned above, there are other genres of literary writing. For example, Saadatullah Safi and Saeedullah Rahmatzai (2020: 2797) submit that “modern literary criticism is written in a variety of genres, including the article, review, survey, essay, literary profile, and bibliographical explanation.” It is worthy of note that literary theories provide insights on the conceptualization of the term “literary writing”.

4. Theoretical Frameworks

This study hinges on Orisawayi’s Development Parameters and Mani’s Concept of “World Literature”.

4.1 Orisawayi's Development Parameters

Orisawayi's (2005: 13-14) development parameters are as follows:

1. Intellectual and mental expansion for the individual person in society;
2. A stable polity with a strong sense of commitment to nationalism/nationhood among the people;
3. Economic development, progress and equitable distribution of national wealth;
4. Socio-political integration of the constituent units that make up the nation;
5. Scientific and technological progress and its application to the improvement of the quality of life of the people;
6. Efficient and functional educational output at all levels;
7. Widely recognized, accepted and practiced democratic structures and systems;
8. Highly enlightened citizenry with 80%-90% achieved level of functional literacy among the people and highly sharpened awareness of individual and collective fundamental rights, with freedom of speech and association;
9. Stable employment for all citizens in private and public sectors of the economy;
10. A highly recognized and respectable network of understanding and positive relations among the constituent units and with other nations of the world;
11. A highly developed network of communication and transport system; and
12. A high sense of motivation among the citizenry towards the achievement of all the parameters of development indices ...

4.2 Mani's Concept of "World Literature"

Mani views work of literature as universal productions in spite of their places of origin. This is because literary writers' use of the elements of literature is sensitive not only to their immediate society, but also to the larger society which is essentially the universe of discourse, where globalization unleashes its trends and practices. Shobha P. (ibid: 37) reports Mani's Concept of World Literature:

Mani argues that in today's globalized world, the cultural or national context of a literary work is not necessarily determined by its place of origin. He argues that contemporary world literature is being produced and disseminated in a public space, facilitated by new media technologies and the Internet's and social media's interconnectedness. The viewpoint of Mani echoes Goethe's remark that "national literature" is now a somewhat meaningless concept, but acquires fresh significance as the world becomes more interconnected than ever before due to technological advances.

5. Literary and Linguistic Perspectives on English within the Context of Globalization

This section of the paper examines the literature of globalization in terms of literary and linguistic perspectives on the English language.

5.1 Literary Perspectives

Discrete aspects of literary perspectives are examined in this section of the paper: elements of literature: and universality of literature.

5.1.1 Elements of Literature

Given the fact that themes and characterization reflect globalization trends (realism), creative writers attempt to explore the vocabulary of English to make inference-making easy for their audience. Laxmi Rawat Chauhan (2018: 171) avers that "globalization has substantially impacted many facets of contemporary literature, including topics, narratives, and literary styles, as a result of the growing connectivity and interdependence of cultures and communities worldwide." Literary writers are sensitive to the globalization trends in the world. Indeed, they are part of such trends and experiences gathered from a wide range of sources. Adèle Ramet (2007) presents the following as sources of ideas:

- Watching the world go by: Watch how people behave in everyday situations, jotting down ideas in your notebooks as they occur to you;
- Keeping an eye on the media: Perhaps the richest sources of ideas are newspapers, television and radio;
- Airports, beaches;
- Coaches, buses, planes, ships;
- Cafés and restaurants;
- Personal experiences;
- Clubs;
- Doctors'/dentists' surgeries;
- Hair dressers;
- School playgrounds;
- Station, etc.

In this era of globalization, capitalist tendencies and materialistic inclinations are common. Literary writers therefore make such societal vices part of their thematic concerns. As a literary theory, New Criticism captures human materialistic indulgence. Literary writers convey such a theme skillfully through language, setting and characterization. In attempting to make globalization-related elements of literature “easy to mean”, literary writers also deploy a literary theory known as Formalism. According to Formalists, the interpretation of a literary text is facilitated by writers’ use of the conventions of language. In this regard, literary texts communicate successfully to a wide range of global audience through writers’ use of grammar and vocabulary conventions. Even when such conventions are violated, meaning is based on such intentional, thematic violation; the literature refers to this process as “defamiliarization”. Viktor Shklovsky (1893-1984) gives insights on defamiliarization by asserting that “literature has the ability to make us see the world anew – to make that which has become familiar because we have been overexposed to it, strange again.” The point here is that within the purview of Formalism, it is worthy of note that the vocabulary of English is so rich that it effectively communicates globalization trends communicated via literature. The broadness of the English lexicon is accentuated by its provision of alternative words from which literary writers and intercultural speakers can make contextually appropriate choices: Consider the examples below:

1. Abatement: reduction, alleviation, ease
2. Abdicate: abandon, forsake, give up
3. Callous: hardened, indifferent, unfeeling
4. Eccentric: odd, strange, uncommon
5. Fabulous: fabricated, amazing, fictitious
6. Machiavellian: crafty, cunning, subtle
7. Magnanimity: generosity, nobility, high-mindedness
8. Naive: unsophisticated, simple, natural
9. Narcotic: sedative, tranquilizer, anaesthetic
10. Obeisance: bow, courtesy, reverence
11. Obesity: fatness, plumpness, rotund
12. Salacious: loose, lustful, carnal
13. Scandalous: disgraceful, inglorious, shameful
14. Tacit: implied, silent, unexpected
15. Taciturn: reticent, dumb, uncommunicative

Literary texts are creative writings which presuppose ample description of things, persons (characters), places (settings), actions, events (activities) and phenomena. Globalization has necessitated the expansion of the English lexicon so much that the global communicative potential of English has been enhanced. Recently, some Nigerian words were added into the English lexicon. Examples include “mama-put” and “japa”. As evidence of the broadness of the English lexicon, consider the following alternative adjectives which describe (qualify) the human body features:

1. HEIGHT: short, tall, average
2. SIZE: slim, plump, heavy, stout, tubby
3. COMPLEXION: black, ebony, tanned, light
4. HAIR: long, short, wavy, spiky, straight, shoulder length, bald, black, gray, blonde
5. FACE: round, long, broad, smooth, wrinkled, dimpled cheek, high cheek bone, tribal/beauty mark
6. EYEBROWS: thick, bushy, trimmed
7. EYES: black, dark brown, blue
8. NOSE: short, long, flat, pointed
9. MOUTH: thick, red, black lips, broad

Feminism is another example of globalization theme or phenomenon captured in literary texts. Such literary texts do not only depict struggle against female discrimination, but also reveal through characterization, what obtains in the contemporary world: gender equality. In the era of globalization, women can aspire for political positions, manage corporate organizations and seek professional careers within and outside their countries. As part of thematic concerns, literary texts convey this shift in value-systems. Westernization and Modernism (literary theories) are thus brought to the fore in Feminist literature. In works of literature, Cultural Materialism attacks societal vices including gender discrimination. Hans Bertens (2014: 148) opines that “literature is not simply a product of history; it actively makes history ... new historicists and cultural materialists treat literary texts in the same way as they treat other text. For their specific purposes – to trace and bring to light relations of power and processes of ideological and cultural constructions – there is no longer a difference between literature and other texts ... in their conviction that culture, including all beliefs and values, is a construction, the new historicists and cultural materialists, are willing to grant that their own assumptions must also be constructed and may therefore be deconstructed.” In the era of globalization, Westernization and Modernism accommodate and justify unconventional sexuality phenomena. Gay marriages and homosexuality are not being viewed as evil as they really are. In literature, such themes are conveyed to depict the ravishing impact of globalization on the pre-established value-systems of human societies. Globalization trends articulated via works of

literature are quite numerous. For example, world economy experiences unprecedented growth. There is massive production to cope with demands. Industrialization has necessitated encroachment on human natural habitat to the detriment of children, youths and adults. Climate change is believed to be a fall-out of the depletion of the ozone layer. In many other ways, deforestation and misuse of aquatic resources pose dangers to human existence. In literature, Ecocriticism examines nature-related themes. In this regard, Hans Bertens (ibid: 225) submits:

Ecocriticism examines representations of landscapes and of nature in its original state: the landscape of pastoral for instance, and wildness, which ... is often represented as a place with a special significance, a place of healing and redemption, or evil and danger where the individual's moral resolve is severely tested. But it may also examine representations of nature in government's reports, developers' plans, ecological studies, government's philosophical treatises, wildlife documentaries (with zoos most people's source of information about wild animals), and other texts and films in which nature plays a role. It may look at the uses of 'nature' in theme parks, at the way 'nature' is given presence inside and outside shopping malls, at roof gardens, at fashions as they come and go in the florist business, at the landscaping of golf courses, at the role of nature in suburbia. Ecocriticism analyses of these representations bring to light the various discourses regarding our natural environment that we have produced since we became consciously aware of it. And, of course, ecocritics pay special attention to the hierarchies that operate in these discourses and that established value systems within them. The most obvious hierarchy privileges us at the expense of the natural world, but there are many others at work in our representations of nature.

Commenting further on Ecocriticism, Jonathan Boote (2000: 8) cited in Hans Bertens (ibid: 202-203) asserts that ecocriticism began in "consciousness-raising, in altering us to the way in which our activities posed an ever-greater threat to our natural environment and in making us think about what it means to live with rather than simply on the earth. Its analyses of the discourses that govern our representations of nature focus, therefore, on the various ways in which these discourses have contributed, and still contribute, to our environmental problems. Absolutely central (although certainly not unique) to the way it deals with issues of representation and all the other issues that fall within the scope is its refusal to adopt a human-centered perspective."

5.1.2 Universality of Literature

In the era of globalization, literature tends towards being a global, universal commodity. This process is informed by the globalization of culture and beliefs to establish a great deal of international unification. Shobha P. (ibid: 34) reports that "Johann Wolfgang Goethe, a German writer and statesman coined the term "global literature" to describe the dissemination of literature from, and to countries around the globe. In letters to Johann Eckermann in 1827, Goethe famously observed, "National literature is now a rather meaningless concept. The time of universal literature is approaching and everyone must try to speed its arrival." Globalization is thus characterized by spread of knowledge and innovations. Shobha P. (ibid: 35) asserts that "literature from around the world is a fantastic tool for examining globalization because it exemplifies how knowledge is exchanged across languages and cultures. Globalization is often characterized as the increasing rate at which nations create power structures that transcend the borders of nation-states. It has a vital role in redefining the knowledge of subjects such as communication, culture, politics, and literature, and in fostering interdisciplinary thought across the humanities. Globalization necessitates social awareness among people in order to share literary knowledge. It is used to communicate not only opinions, but also culture and tradition, as well as to consider the problems of citizens and find solutions that are timely. Globalization is a broad idea that facilitates our comprehension of world-class literature (Bauman, 1998)." The phenomenon of "Modern World Literature" is promoted by the spread of translation efforts on literary texts, many of which have been translated into many languages of the world for cross-regional readership. Providing insights on the term "global literature", Laxmi Rawat Chauhan (ibid: 171) posits that "according to O' Brien, Marx and Engels acknowledged the presence of a global literature that developed as a result of the ongoing revolutionization of bourgeois production when they write during one of the pivotal periods of European nationalism. They also noted how this literature had crossed national and cultural barriers. One of the first elites to be globally connected – materially and artistically – was literary elite who had a grasp on exotic narrative confections produced beyond their own national and regional settings. Even prior to Marx and Engels or Goethe making explicit pronouncements about "world literature" in the 19th century, there were, however, additional indications. Early cultural migrations can be detected in literary genres like the fabliau, autobiography, and Mennpean satire; literature was global before it was ever national."

5.2 Linguistic Perspectives

Linguistic perspectives on English in the context of globalization can be construed in terms of: the global status of English; and nation-building.

5.2.1 The Global Status of English

English is a global language for different reasons part of which is its success in former British colonies including Nigeria. Akere (2006: 5-6) identifies five factors which inform the success of English in Nigeria:

- (a.) English can be described as a product of linguistic imperialism bestowed by colonialism;
- (b.) The introduction of certification system in Nigeria's educational programmes, with ordinary pass and Credit pass in English, as a measure of adequacy for higher education (Even to read French or Hausa or Yoruba or Igbo in any Nigerian University, at the Bachelor level, you must have a Credit pass in English);
- (c.) A good working knowledge of English language is considered a prerequisite for obtaining government jobs;
- (d.) Establishment of educational institutions and the introduction of English as a subject of study, and a medium of instruction;
- (e.) The establishment of the British Council in 1935, and charter in 1940 to promote a wider knowledge of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and the English language abroad.

Rohmah Zuliatu (2005: 107) clarification of the term "global language" is worthy of scholarly attention:

About fifty years ago the notion of English as a true global language was merely a theoretical prediction which is still diffuse and vague. However, realities have created it as a real world language at the present time. People in every part of the world feel its urgent role in their life: for academic purposes, for business goals, and for other purposes. English is spoken by people throughout the world as their first language, second language and foreign language. Indeed, English is now a world language. English as a world language is not merely an international language. The notion of international language can be understood as a language which is used in any international communication which involves people from two or more countries. Japanese is an international language, but it is not a global language...

The literature provides sufficient reasons to view the English language as a global language. For instance, Nataliya Todorova and Anna Todorova (2018: 336) report statistical claims of the British Council on the global position and functions of the English language:

- English has official or special status in at least 75 countries, with a total population of more than two billion;
- one out of four of the world's population speak English to some level of competence; demand from the other three quarters is increasing;
- more than two thirds of the world's scientists read in English;
- three quarters of the world's mail are written in English;
- 80 per cent of the world's electronically stored information is in English.

Bello, O. Rachael and Oni-Buraimoh, O. Olawunmi (2017: 102) present different reasons why the English language readily comes to mind as a global language:

- It is the language of a number of past colonies;
- Apart from its being one of the languages used in international organizations such as UNO and AU, English is also versatile and it enjoys a wide spread;
- It is the most studied language (Research had it that yearly, 1, 500 million people would opt to learn English; 84 million, French; 30 million, Chinese);
- It is one of the easiest languages to learn when compared with Chinese, German, French, Spanish, Arabic, Korean, and Japanese. The most difficult languages of the world to learn are Arabic, Chinese, Korean and Japanese (Arranged in order of their degree of difficulty);
- A reasonable percentage of information found in the internet is in English;
- It has a rich and in-depth history.

Laxman Jnawali (2024: 15-16) submits that "this language has worked as a bridge among various bilingual and multilingual communities where English language has been used as second or foreign language ... The language has been very popular in social media as well. People from multilingual communities are actively involved in learning English as their second and foreign language. People are learning IELTS, TOEFL, PTE, GRE and many others in order to go to the foreign countries for various purposes. According to David Crystal (ibid: 112), "since the 1960s, English has become the normal medium of instruction in higher education for many countries – and is increasingly used in several where the language has no official status ... The English language teaching (ELT) business has become one of the major growth industries around the world in the past half-century. However, its relevance to the growth of English as a world language goes back much further."

5.2.2 Nation-building

In recognition of the importance of knowledge, science and technology in the sustainable growth and development of a nation, language policy frameworks were evolved in different African countries to explore linguistic insights for the purpose of national development. The National Policy of Education in Nigeria is worthy of attention in this regard. The communicative functions of any human language are the reasons for its importance in any nation. Building a nation means making progress in the nation. Connor & Deutsch (1971: 661) define “nation” as “a community of shared meanings or more broadly still, group of people who have interlocking habits of communication.” Anderson (1996) defines “nation” as “a clearly defined territory which (i) is recognized internationally as a state (ii) is presided over by a government able to make and enforce independent decisions concerning domestic policy and law and foreign policy and (iii) is permanently occupied by a specific population.” In any nation, language policy on education in the era of globalization is recognition of the fact that human capacity development is instrumental in national development. In spheres of nation-hood, acquired skills are translated into productivity for the overall growth and development of a nation. See Dada (2010), Bamgbose (1972; 1991) for insights on language planning in multilingual Nigeria. Appel and Muysken (1987: 46) reports the goals of language policy:

- (a) Choose a national language;
- (b) Develop or cultivate the chosen language;
- (c) Foster the spread of the language;
- (d) Decide on the position of the minority languages;
- (e) Decide also on the functions expected of indigenous languages, especially the minority ones.

Indeed, a sociolinguistic overview of globalization investigates the significance of language in nation-building. Bello Buraimoh, O. Olawunmi (ibid: 100) defines language as “a unique property that belongs to the human race. It is a means of communication between two or more people and to a very large extent, the development of man politically, socially, economically, etc., depends on the use of language. Indeed, language permeates all aspects of human endeavor. Language is an integral part of culture, a reflection of many features of a given culture ...” Obiegbu Ifeyinwa (2014: 87) defines language as “a creation of man ‘social needs. Like all other living creatures, we depend on the air, water and earth around us, and in the same way, society depends upon language for its very existence. For effective national development, language plays a central role, particularly in terms of such agents of development as literacy and communication. This is clearly understandable because it is through language that man has to plan ... Apart from the planning, man uses language to instruct and evaluate his programmes.” Topado and Smith (2011) construe development in terms of three dimensions: economic dimension (satisfaction of basic needs); psychological dimension (positive view of “self” as obtainable in any person); and social dimension (freedom that individuals have or enjoy as their right).

Within the context of globalization, English is simply for national development in different regions of the world. Obasi (1987) defines national development as “the progressive transformation of the economic, social and political structures of a society from relatively less complex, less efficient and less desirable forms to relatively more complex, more efficient and more desirable forms.” In addition, Akaegbobi, Oby et al. (2001: 77) submits that “the imperatives of national development stems from the recognition that besides what the whole world has professed to achieve, each nation has to devise home grown mechanism to improve the quantity and quality of lives of their citizens. It is also built on the understanding that all countries of the world do not share the same needs. In national development each country focuses on what it considers important in the improvement of lives of its citizens ... national development is not a destination. Thus, there is no point which a country will reach and it will conclude that it has attained national development. We rather say that national development is a process, a continuous process ...”

As a language for nation-building, English is used for national cohesion, integration, solidarity and mobilization. The language is void of ethnic sentiments. It is neutral and void of the divisive potential that indigenous languages in multilingual nations spur to threaten nation-hood. Wardhaugh R. and Janet M. Fuller (2015: 9) note that “solidarity refers to the motivations which cause individuals to act together and to fulfill a common bond which influences their social actions. Thus the concept of solidarity is intertwined with both identity formation and group formation.” The common linguistic basis that constitutes a requisite for the existence of any nation is provided by English. So with English as the common tongue to all the ethnic groups, the collective sentiment of belonging together despite the individual or ethnic differences is forged. Related to the discussion is the fact that Nigerian Nationalism or collective identity is stamped on national institutions through the medium of English.” In a similar vein, David Crystal’s (ibid: 146) submits extensively on the communicative potential of the English lexicon:

Most adaptation in new English relates to vocabulary, in the form of new words (borrowings – from several hundred language sources, in such areas as Nigeria), word-formations, word-meanings, collocations and idiomatic phrases. There are many cultural domains likely to motivate new words, as speakers find themselves adapting the language to meet fresh communicative needs. A country’s biogeographical uniqueness will generate potentially large numbers of words for animals, fish, birds, insects, plants, trees, rocks, rivers and so on

– as well as the issues to do with land management and interpretation which is an especially important feature of the lifestyle of many indigenous peoples. There will be words for foodstuffs, drinks, medicines, drugs, and the practices associated with eating ... The country's mythology and religion, and practices in astronomy and astrology, will bring forth new names for personalities, beliefs and rituals. The country's oral and perhaps written literature will give rise to distinctive names in sagas, poems, oratory and folktales. There will be a body of local laws and customs, with their own terminology. The culture will have its own technology with its own terms – such as for vehicles, house – buildings, weapons, clothing, ornaments and musical instruments. The whole world of leisure and the arts will have a linguistic dimension – names of dances, musical styles, games, sports – as will distinctiveness in body appearance (such as hair styles, tattoos, decoration). Virtually any aspect of social structure can generate complex naming systems – local government, family relationships, clubs and societies, and so on ... So, when a community adopts a new language, and starts to use it in relation to all areas of life, there is inevitably going to be a great deal of lexical creation.

6. Conclusion

Globalization is a new and evolving phenomenon in the contemporary world. It determines the scheme of things in so many ways as it dislodges previous ways of doing things at the international level. Consequently, countries attempt to be part of the dynamics and advantages of globalization for the main purpose of delivering the dividends of good governance to the populace. Literature, being a representation of life, is not exempted from the influence of globalization. Its approach to the elements of literature and presentation of contents are clearly depictions of the fall-outs of globalization. English is indeed a global language. Its position on the global stage is not incidental as shown by historical factors and its wide lexicon which facilitates communication both in literature and governance. However, if English is to be maximally instrumental in nation-building within the context of globalization, the corpora of regional Englishes should be made similar to Standard British English as much as possible, through the efforts of the educational system of any country. Considering the significance of English within the context of globalization, positive attitudes towards it should be encouraged by stakeholders. Adegbija (1994) is instructive on language attitudes discourse. Negative attitudes are instigated by “linguistic nationalism”, which is simply agitation against the dominance of an alien language over indigenous languages in a country. While such agitations are natural, it must be understood that a framework for the co-existence of an official language or *lingua franca* with other languages in any nation is necessary to benefit from the communication-based benefits of globalization which English guarantees in the contemporary world.

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